

Electronically REconfigurable Superstrate (ERES) Antenna

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Abstract—In this paper, we propose Electronically REconfigurable Superstrate (ERES) antenna design to provide simple, yet effective, beam steering capabilities to increase connectivity between wireless sensor network (WSN) nodes. The proposed design involves the superstrate layer concept, proposed originally to increase gain of microstrip patch antennas. By grouping parasitic patches within the designed superstrate layer and introducing a switching circuit with PIN diodes, it has been possible to create sections that can be steered using only 4 digital input output ports. Simulation results indicate, that, by shortening each section independently to the ground, it is possible to steer the main antenna beam electronically. In consequence, the proposed antenna can successfully be used to improve connectivity in WSN nodes relying on inexpensive transceivers and operating in demanding industrial conditions.

Index Terms—Switched-beam antenna, reconfigurable antenna, steerable antenna, electronically steerable parasitic array radiator (ESPAR) antenna, electronically reconfigurable superstrate (ERES) antenna, superstrate antenna, wireless sensor network (WSN).

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern wireless systems create a demand for reconfigurable antennas, especially with respect to changing antenna radiation pattern in time, in order to determine direction-of-arrival (DoA) of surrounding radio frequency (RF) signal sources [1], determine their position [2] or improve energy efficiency and connectivity of the whole network by directing antenna beam [3]. To be applied in wireless sensor network (WSN) nodes, which contain simple and inexpensive microcontrollers and RF transceivers, reconfigurable antennas cannot rely on complex solutions, e.g. digital signal processing (DSP) units, that can cause high costs and energy consumption of a final system.

One of the most efficient structures providing the possibility of steering the main beam direction is an Electronically Steerable Parasitic Array Radiator (ESPAR) antenna [5]. This antenna consists of an active monopole surrounded by circular array of 6 passive elements connected to varactor diodes. By changing reactances' values one can steer antenna main beam electronically using a DSP unit having 6 digital-to-analog (DAC) converters providing the correct bias voltages. Such antenna can successfully be adopted to WSN applications by using single-pole, double-throw SPDT switches instead of varactor diodes [6], [7]. By connecting to the ground or leaving open passive elements' ends, one can control antenna radiation pattern using WSN

node's microcontroller digital input output (DIO) ports connected to the switches. However, due to the fact that all elements are monopoles, the resulting antenna will have radiation pattern shape of the conical beam, similar to the dipole antenna, with a deep minimum in the direction aligned with the monopoles' axis, beneath the antenna when the antenna is mounted on a ceiling. This may cause connectivity problems in demanding practical indoor scenarios, like production sites or factories, in which a WSN base station equipped with ESPAR the antenna is placed in high distance above mobile WSN nodes and uses steering capability to increase connectivity with nodes working in challenging propagation conditions [2].

To steer antenna radiation pattern in both elevation and horizontal planes one can use antenna concepts, in which passive elements form a grid of small metallic patches interconnected with each other through switches [8]-[11]. Based on this concept, a reconfigurable pixel surface in form of an additional, partially reflective layer over a radiating patch has been proposed [12]-[14]. Such layer provides radiation pattern reconfigurability to the conventional patch antenna. However, to set up the radiation pattern, one has to use high number of MEMS switches or PIN diodes interconnecting a numerous passive elements. As a consequence, this would impact the overall antenna cost and, due to many DIO ports, may also complicate beam steering process.

In this paper, an antenna with Electronically REconfigurable Superstrate (ERES) is proposed to achieve steering capabilities that requires only 4 DIO ports. The structure relies on a concept proposed in [15] that consists of a patch antenna and a superstrate layer, which is an additional dielectric layer containing an array of passive rectangular patches suspended about half wavelength above the feed patch. Using such superstrate layer containing 5×5 array of square parasitic patches it has been possible to narrow the beam of a conventional patch antenna and to increase the original antenna gain by 5.4 dB at 5.8 GHz in a simple and low-cost way [15]. We have further developed the concept by introducing elements allowing for reconfigurability of the superstrate, so the main beam can be electronically steered from a simple microcontroller or an RF transceiver being a part of WSN nodes. Proposed electronically reconfigurable superstrate (ERES) antenna prototype designed for 2.4 GHz frequency band, which is commonly used in WSN applications, has been verified in numerical simulations.

II. ANTENNA DESIGN

The reconfigurable antenna structure has been developed in two stages. In the first step antenna with a superstrate layer has been designed based on the procedure available in the literature [15]. Afterwards, a switching mechanism has been proposed to provide simple, yet effective, steering mechanism to the obtained antenna model.

Fig. 1. Geometry of the antenna with superstrate layer (side view), in which parasitic patches are facing the feed patch.

Fig. 2. Geometry of the proposed superstrate layer with dimensions (in millimeters). In the white boxes, sizes of square patches are presented, while in the yellow boxes distances between them on the dielectric layer are shown.

Fig. 3. Simulated radiation pattern in E plane of the proposed antenna with and without superstrate layer.

A. Microstrip Patch Antenna with Superstrate Layer

The proposed antenna structure consists of two separate layers: a feed layer containing a conventional patch antenna

placed on a thin substrate and a superstrate layer, which is a dielectric plane containing an array of passive patches, suspended in the air above the feed patch. Both layers were designed and optimized in Altair FEKO simulator at the center frequency 2.44 GHz using FR4 substrate ($\epsilon_r = 4.47$, $\tan \delta = 0.02$).

For the feed layer, a microstrip patch antenna with linear polarization and centrally placed feeding point connected to SMA connector has been chosen and optimized at the center frequency. Then, over the resulting $28 \times 37 \text{ mm}$ patch, an additional dielectric layer has been placed approximately half the wavelength above the ground plane, as presented in Fig. 1. At the bottom of the superstrate layer, an array of 25 parasitic patches has been inserted as 5×5 symmetrical grid structure, similar to the one proposed in [15]. The superstrate layer's dimensions after performed optimization are presented in Fig. 2. The resulting input reflection coefficient equals to -15.66 dB at the center frequency, while the obtained simulated radiation pattern is presented in Fig. 3. As it can easily be noticed, superstrate layer presence decreases 3 dB beamwidth and also increases antenna gain.

B. Switching Mechanism for Superstrate Layer

To implement radiation pattern steering in the designed antenna, a simple switching mechanism has been proposed as a control network embedded within the antenna structure on both sides of the superstrate layer. To this end, the superstrate has been divided into 4 areas, which are called switching section, and edges of the dielectric on both sides of the superstrate layer were covered with metallization as shown in Fig. 4. To these metallized edges, the ground plane from the lower side of the feed layer of the antenna has been connected to four corners with a silver-coated copper wire having 1.5 mm in diameter, which substituted plastic spacers in Fig. 1.

Fig. 4. Switching circuit for reconfigurable superstrate layer (see text for explanations).

In order to create four switching sections, parasitic patches in the corners of the array were grouped by four and then divided into pairs. The elements in these pairs were connected to each other and to the ground via the edges of the superstrate layer by PIN diodes as presented in Fig. 4. Additionally, in the steering circuit on the top of the superstrate layer, four lines provide voltages V_A, V_B, V_C, V_D through the via holes to the elements that are at the bottom of the superstrate layer of each section. As a consequence, when appropriate bias voltage is applied at the switching section on the top of the superstrate layer, the proper steering current is injected by the resistor to the patch and PIN diodes turning them into forward polarization operation. As a result, all section patches at the bottom of the superstrate layer will be shortened to the ground.

Fig. 5. Simulated 3D normalized radiation pattern at 2.44 GHz.

Available switching configurations for the proposed antenna design can be denoted in a form of a steering vector $\vec{V} = [v_A, v_B, v_C, v_D]$ that can easily be implemented in a microcontroller memory [6]. All the values within \vec{V} reflect section states. The value equal to 1 means that the corresponding section is connected to the ground via its PIN diodes, while 0 means that passive patches within the corresponding section are not connected to each other nor to the ground.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The proposed antenna with reconfigurable superstrate layer has been implemented in Altair FEKO simulator. In the conducted simulations, 180Ω resistors, 68 nH L-14C68NJV4S inductors and BAP142LX PIN diodes has been used as models based on data provided by the manufacturers.

Using the steering vector \vec{V} one can change the direction of the main beam electronically by reconfiguration of interconnections between superstrate layer passive patches. Therefore, we have conducted four different simulations, in which a single section has been connected to the ground, while the remaining three were left open. As results in Fig. 5 and

Fig. 6 indicate, when a section is shorted, it influences the antenna beam and thus the radiation pattern changes. In consequence, the antenna radiates in the opposite direction to the shorted section. Additionally, simulated reflection coefficients in Fig. 7 indicate the similar resonant frequency for each of the four configurations.

Fig. 2. Simulated radiation pattern in H plane ($\theta = 35^\circ$) for the considered configurations at 2.44 GHz.

Fig. 7. Simulated reflection coefficient for the proposed antenna for all considered configurations (see text for explanations).

TABLE I
MAIN BEAM PARAMETERS FOR ALL THE CONSIDERED CONFIGURATIONS AT 2.44 GHz.

steering vector	φ_{max}	θ_{max}	$\Delta\varphi_{3dB}$	$\Delta\theta_{3dB}$
$\vec{V} = [1, 0, 0, 0]$	123°	4°	67° ... 230°	0° ... 48°
$\vec{V} = [0, 1, 0, 0]$	237°	4°	127° ... 295°	0° ... 48°
$\vec{V} = [0, 0, 1, 0]$	306°	5°	255° ... 54°	0° ... 48°
$\vec{V} = [0, 0, 0, 1]$	54°	5°	303° ... 106°	0° ... 48°

Simulation results confirm that ERES antenna is able to change beam direction by reconfiguring the interconnections in the proposed superstrate layer. Moreover, the results gathered in Table I indicate that using only four different steering vectors it is possible to cover the whole 2D hemisphere in a practical WSN scenario, in which the antenna is placed on a ceiling and have to steer its beam towards WSN nodes placed in an industrial area beneath.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, new antenna structure with electronically reconfigurable superstrate (ERES) has been proposed and analyzed. The original concept of superstrate layer, introduced in the literature to increase gain of microstrip patch antennas, has been modified. In the proposed antenna design, passive patches within the superstrate were grouped into 4 sections and a switching circuit with PIN diodes has been proposed. In consequence, using only 4 digital input output ports in a microcontroller it is possible to shorten independently each section to the ground, which has been used to steer ERES antenna radiation pattern. Simulation results indicate, that the proposed antenna can successfully be used in inexpensive WSN nodes operating improving connectivity in demanding industrial conditions, as the proposed switching mechanism provides efficient coverage of the entire angular range in the horizontal plane using only four switching configurations.

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